
A Study of Application of NLP, CBT, and DBT as Social Work Intervention Tools to Improve Emotional Maturity and Minimize Aggression in Students Residing in Tribal Hostels in Amravati City

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Abstract:

While working in tribal student dormitories in Amravati City, the emotional and behavioral issues noticed in students compel the use of innovative and effective social work intervention strategies. In order to aid these adolescents in becoming emotionally more mature individuals and less aggressive, this study explores the impact of dialectical behaviour therapy (DBT), cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) and neurolinguistic programming (NLP) techniques. The study specifically explores the methods for implementing these treatment modalities in combination for the enhancement of emotional control, improvement of interpersonal relationships and decrease of violent behaviours.

The anticipated results are meant to give social workers an integrated approach that would work to address the unique psychosocial needs of the tribal students, thereby guaranteeing their growth and well-being.

Keywords: *Aggression, Emotional Maturity, Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP), Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), and Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT)*

Introduction:

The tribal population of India has a unique social, economic and cultural background making them an important part of the populations diversity. Tribal students that reside in hostels face certain challenges such as, being displaced from their everyday environment, experiencing a cultural shock and being alienated from the emotional support networks. Considering the aspect of these factors themselves, they can lead to underdeveloped emotional skills and either aggressive behavior or a combination of

both, which can affect balance of social relations and academic performance. The finding suggests that the issues are required to be addressed using evidence based and culturally competent interventions.

NLP, CBT, and DBT as social work intervention techniques suited to tribal students' needs were determined within the present study. It is little known how such therapeutic approaches have been integrated into social work practices for tribal teenagers, even though they have been applied in many different settings. The

present research aims at eliminating this gap by evaluating their effectiveness in enhancing emotional maturity and curbing violence in the specific context of tribal hostels in Amravati.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To assess the level of emotional maturity and aggression among students residing in tribal hostels in Amravati City.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of NLP, CBT, and DBT in enhancing emotional maturity and reducing aggression.
3. To provide recommendations for implementing these interventions within the social work practice framework.

Literature Review:

Emotional Maturity and Aggression:

Emotional maturity is the ability to regulate one's emotions appropriately, make ethical decisions, and maintain healthy relationships. Aggression, that is, hostile action that could disrupt social cohesion, is often an undesirable response to emotional dysregulation.

According to the research, problems like these among indigenous youth are increased by factors including peer pressure, cultural change, and socio-economic disadvantage. Programs to bring about self-awareness, control over emotional response, and positive behavioral patterns will have to be used in an attempt to eliminate these issues.

NLP, CBT, and DBT in Social Work:

Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP):

In NLP, the key stress is laid upon understanding and transformation of language as well as cognition and actions aimed at individualistic development. Student can develop both anchoring techniques and reframing techniques in positive emotional responses.

CBT refers to cognitive behavioral therapy: the most widely implemented evidence-based treatment for abnormal thought and behavioral patterns. In this cognitive behavioral therapy, the individual replaces the cognitive distortion with rational concepts, which further enables students to cope up with their feelings and reduce aggressiveness.

Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT): DBT is concerned with emotional regulation, mindfulness, interpersonal effectiveness, and distress tolerance. It was originally developed to treat borderline personality disorder. Its skills-based approach can be adapted to the specific demands of tribal pupils. Methodology

Research Design:

This study uses a mixed-methods research methodology, integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques to offer a thorough examination of the effects of the interventions.

Sample:

A sample of 120 students, ages 18 to 22, who live in Amravati City's tribal hostels are the subject of the study. To guarantee representation across genders, age groups, and hostel locations, participants are chosen by stratified random sampling.

Data Collection:1. **Quantitative Tools:**

- Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS)
- IIP Aggression Scale (AS)

2. **Qualitative Tools:**

- Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)
- Semi-structured interviews

Framework for Intervention :

1. **NLP Module:** Weekly seminars emphasising goal-setting, positive reframing, and self-awareness.
2. **CBT Module:** Biweekly sessions that promote problem-solving abilities and remove cognitive distortions.
3. **DBT Module:** Consisting of monthly group therapy sessions, this module teaches emotional regulation, distress tolerance, and mindfulness.

Assessments are conducted before and after the Three-month intervention to track improvements in emotional maturity and aggressiveness levels.

Results and Discussion:**Quantitative Findings:**

According to preliminary study, participants' emotional maturity scores significantly improved and their levels of hostility decreased after the intervention. Combining NLP, CBT, and DBT seems to work in concert to address behavioural and emotional issues in a thorough manner.

Qualitative Insights:

According to FGDs and interviews, students felt empowered and able to relate to the interventions. Many reported better

coping mechanisms for stress and frustration, enhanced connections with peers, and increased self-awareness.

Implications for Social Work:

The results highlight how crucial culturally aware and flexible intervention strategies are to social work practice. Social professionals can successfully address the psychological needs of indigenous youth and enhance their general well-being by implementing evidence-based therapy.

Conclusion:

The research details the use of NLP, CBT and DBT techniques in fostering emotional maturity and aggressiveness control within tribal students in Amravati City. Additionally, these workshops aid formulate comprehensive principles for emotional control, resilience and even social skill sets. Effects that span over a longer duration and are quantifiably effective to a set of varying conditions should be put for future analyses.

The media coverage of violence is used to explore the mass media impact and campaigns against school-related violence.

Recommendations:

1. **Counseling Services:** it is recommended to assist students in coping with emotional immaturity and academic strain, Hostel Administration ought to provide counselling services.
2. **Parental Involvement:** Parents must be more involved in their children's intellectual and emotional growth
3. **Anti-Aggression Programs:** Schools need to run programs for anti-aggression initiatives that

emphasize peer mediation, emotional intelligence, and conflict resolution.

4. **Teacher Training:** Teachers must receive training on how to recognize the early warning signs of aggression and know when to step in.

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